

CHARACTERISTICS OF USING MUSIC IN PHYSICAL EXERCISES

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Abstract: This article discusses the methodology of using music in physical education classes. Also, musical rhythm organizes actions, improves the mood of students. Positive emotions create a desire to perform actions more energetically, which increases their effect on the body, helps to increase work capacity, as well as recovery and active rest.

Key words: physical training, musical genre, musical accompaniment, methodological technique, emotional background, healing effect.

One of the tasks solved at health-improving lessons is getting students a positive emotional charge from physical activity. Music is one of the strongest stimulants of human emotions. It has been proven that its effect activates the physiological and psychological functions of those involved:

- ❖ Decreased heart rate;
- ❖ Increases metabolism and activates the work of internal organs;
- ❖ The mood of those involved improves;
- ❖ Helps to fight monotony in the classroom;
- ❖ Helps to overcome growing fatigue;

Back at the end of the last century, the physiologist Tarkhanov proved that major music increases the efficiency of muscles, positively affects the nature and rhythm of breathing, heartbeat, and causes positive emotions. Later, Bekhterev traced the dependence of the frequency of breathing and pulse on music: with calm melodies, breathing becomes deeper and more uniform, harmonic harmonies slow down the pulse. The strong sound of music accelerates fatigue. Melodic and rhythmic music tones up and revitalizes the biochemical processes taking place in the body and rebuilds the nervous apparatus and psyche. Using functional music as a stimulant, you can increase the rhythmic processes of the body, make them more economical in terms of energy costs, which means you can increase the time of work before fatigue. In combination with physical exercises, music creates a positive emotional background, as a rule, dictates the pace of the exercise. Music is an essential part of the aerobics program, so certain rules must be followed when choosing it.

A fast pace and rhythm drops are possible only with sufficient coordination and physical fitness of those involved. It is necessary to ensure that the phonograms set the correct pace for performing movements throughout the entire time of the

lesson. Performing an aerobics complex to music without stopping allows you to maintain a high motor density of classes, making them extremely emotional. At the same time, the tempo of music is of great importance, since it largely determines the intensity of movements. The pace of movements is a temporary measure of their repetitions. It is measured by the number of movements repeated per unit of time and determines the frequency of movements. The pace is the reciprocal of the duration of movements: the longer the duration of one movement, the lower the pace, and vice versa.

The music used in the classes is the canvas, the quality of which largely determines the effectiveness and attractiveness of the health-improving class for those involved. When conducting classes, modern music is widely used, on which dance movements corresponding to it in style are “superimposed”. This predetermines the need for appropriate training of the teacher. From the ability of the teacher to conduct various types of exercises with musical accompaniment, to enrich the lessons with aesthetic content, to draw the attention of students to expressive, precise and beautiful movements, the effectiveness of classes to some extent depends.

In repetitive cyclic movements, tempo can serve as an indicator of the perfection of technique. With fatigue, the pace of movements changes: it can rise and fall.

As the tempo of movements changes, their rhythm changes. Rhythm is a temporary measure of the ratio of parts of a movement. Rhythmic exercises contribute to the development of musicality, a sense of rhythm among those involved, bring up the ability to perform movements of various duration and amplitude, combine them in time and space, and also influence the development of coordination, orientation in space, and speed of reaction.

In recreational activities, the main source of the influence of music on the working capacity of the student is the ability of a person to assimilate rhythms from the outside.

Classes with musical accompaniment are of great health and hygiene importance. The musical rhythm organizes movements, improves the mood of those involved. Positive emotions cause the desire to perform movements more energetically, which enhances their effect on the body, contributes to increased efficiency, as well as recovery and active recreation. Music can also be used as a learning factor as movements are easier to remember.

With the help of music, it becomes possible to regulate the load of motor activity. Rhythm gives a sense of satisfaction, so it not only facilitates work, but also

delivers aesthetic pleasure. This is the basis of the positive impact of recreational activities with musical accompaniment on the activity of the body. Music is a frequency-impulsive code, one of the most effective means of influencing a person's mental state. Sparta is one of the states of the Ancient World that used music in physical education and sports. Pythagoras himself contributed to the widespread introduction of music into physical education on a scientific and theoretical basis.

In domestic physical culture, in particular aerobics, the idea of musical stimulation of physical performance during training sessions has arisen and is gaining momentum. It improves mood, endurance, the level of manifestation of muscle strength, speed, agility. As a result, the overall performance is increased. Music, causing certain emotional tensions in a person, actively affects the human psyche, the intensity of metabolic processes, the respiratory, cardiovascular systems, increases the tone of the brain, blood circulation. Properly selected music during classes has a positive effect on human activity, contributing to such a rhythmic tuning of the body, in which physiological processes proceed more efficiently. Positive emotional arousal at the sound of pleasant melodies enhances attention, activates the central nervous system and stimulates muscle activity, and helps to increase the working capacity of those involved. Thus, music is one of the means of improving the effectiveness of recreational activities and it can be considered one of the methodological methods of teaching and educating those involved.

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